

Supplemental material

Measuring semantic memory using associative and dissociative retrieval tasks

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1. Effect of trial order on free-associate and dissociate retrieval latency

The effect of trial order on retrieval latency was tested by linear-mixed effect model. This LMEM included the main effect of retrieval condition (FA vs DA), main effect of trial order (stimuli presented in the First vs the Second block), and their interaction (note that random intercepts were estimated for participants and word stimuli). The results showed a significant main effect of trial order, $F(1, 21933) = 122.62$, $p < .001$, indicating that retrieving a concept took longer when the same stimuli were presented in the other condition before. Moreover, we observed a significant interaction between the trial order and retrieval condition factors, $F(1, 22039) = 11.95$, $p < .001$, showing that trial order slowed down responding on DA trials significantly more than on FA trials (see Tab. S1). Finally, these effects did not change as a function of ADT form in three-way interaction (Trial order \times Condition \times Form), $p = .369$.

Table S1. Table of contrasts from linear-mixed effect model testing the effect of trial order and retrieval condition on response latency

Condition	Trial order		Comparison		Contrast	
	First	Second	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Estimate	SE
FA	3.341 \pm 0.160	3.601 \pm 0.160	5.457	< .001	0.260	0.048
DA	5.998 \pm 0.161	6.495 \pm 0.161	10.115	< .001	0.497	0.049

Note. Values represent estimated marginal means \pm standard error of response time in seconds. Asymptotic results are shown due to large sample size.

2. Results of parallel analyses conducted on data related to psycholinguistic and associative properties, and cognitive performance data

Figure S1. Scree plots from parallel analyses showing Eigenvalues of the components extracted from the observed correlation matrices against the 95th-percentile Eigenvalues of the components extracted from the simulated matrices ($N = 500$). Only the components with observed Eigenvalue surpassing the simulated Eigenvalue were deemed significant. Parallel analyses indicated two-dimensional solutions for the *psycholinguistic* (PL) and *associative properties* (AP) data, and unidimensional solutions for cognitive constructs estimated respectively from the *ADT free-associate* (FA), *ADT dissociate* (DA), *ADT inhibition cost* (IC), *working memory* (WM), *processing speed* (PS), *verbal fluency* (VF), and *associative combination* (AC) data.

3. Results of principal component analyses conducted on data related to psycholinguistic and associative properties, and cognitive performance data

Table S2. Summary table of principal component analyses conducted on psycholinguistic data (Vividness, Affective tone), Associative properties data (Typicality, Topology), and respective cognitive constructs data

Component	Indicator	Loading (λ)	KMO	Explained variance (%)	ω
Vividness	Concreteness	.93	.63	56%	.85
	Imageability	.88			
	Context availability	.77			
Affective tone	Emotional valence	.91	.76	44%	.83
	Arousal	-.93			
Associative typicality	1 st assoc frequency	.93	.71	50%	.96
	Freq decrease (β)	-.99			
	Freq intercept	.94			
Associative topology	Modularity	-.81	.76	50%	.88
	Shortest path length	-.84			
	Clustering coefficient	.74			
	Global efficiency	.96			
Associative retrieval	ADT - FA _A	.96	.77	89%	.94
	ADT - FA _B	.94			
	ADT - FA _C	.93			
Dissociative retrieval	ADT - DA _A	.95	.75	90%	.94
	ADT - DA _B	.95			
	ADT - DA _C	.95			
Inhibition cost	ADT - IC _A	.93	.75	84%	.91
	ADT - IC _B	.90			
	ADT - IC _C	.92			
Working memory	Alpha span	.83	.69	68%	.76
	Operational span	.83			
	Rotational span	.80			
Processing speed	Digit-symbol subst.	.86	.65	65%	.74
	Letter matching	.80			
	Choice resp. time	.75			
Verbal fluency	Animals	.78	.67	67%	.75
	Occupations	.86			
	Tools	.80			
Associative combination	AC _A	.90	.74	79%	.87
	AC _B	.88			
	AC _C	.89			

Note: KMO – Keiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy. ω – McDonald's omega coefficient of internal consistency. Vividness and affective tone [positive vs negative] scores ($r = -.279$), as well as associative typicality and topology [highly vs sparsely connected] scores ($r = -.271$), were weakly negatively correlated.

4. Cronbach-Mesbah-Curves for ADT retrieval measures

Figure S2. In the Cronbach-Mesbah-Curve, the trials (ADT stimulus words) are ordered by their relative contribution to the estimated Cronbach's α (i.e., trials that maximize α are on the left side of the x axis). As depicted by the monotonously increasing trends, the ADT measures are homogeneous and only a fraction of the best performing trials is required to achieve the required level of reliability for research ($r \geq 0.7$) and clinical application ($r \geq 0.9$, marked by dashed horizontal line).

5. Visual demonstration of associative typicality and topology scores on selected ADT stimulus words

Figure S3. Illustrative display of associative properties for ADT stimulus words with high and low typicality (top) and topology (bottom) scores. Notice in the upper section of the figure markedly higher proportional occurrence of the strongest associations and a steeper decrease in the occurrence of subsequent association for the words with high typicality scores (“Palm” and “Sky”) compared to words with low typicality scores (“Iron” and “Thief”) showing noticeably smaller offset between the occurrence of their most frequent and less frequent associations. The networks in the bottom section of the figure show considerably denser and stronger connections between the associations of words with high topology score (“Sky” and “Thief”) than between the associations of words with low topology score (“Palm” and “Iron”) which conversely exhibit substantial partitioning, sparser and weaker connections. **Note:** Vertical dashed line and solid red line in the upper-section plots demarcate the five most frequent associations and frequency decrease slope (β) across the ten most occurring associations, respectively. The colour (from blue to red) and size of the nodes in the bottom-section networks correspond to the frequency of associations, whereas the width of the links reflects the weight of connections (LogDice score). Greyed areas mark the clusters of associations identified by the Louvain modularity algorithm. Only associations (nodes) with frequency ≥ 5 are depicted. Networks were visualized in Gephi software (version 0.9.4).